

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A prototype simulation model to investigate the spread of tungro (RTD) viruses in a rice crop

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RTD causes major losses in tropical lowland irrigated rice production. Key questions relating to the management of the disease remain unanswered. These include the relative importance of primary disease spread into plantings and secondary spread within plantings; the role of individual vector species; the importance of different infection sources; and the impact of control options, such as insecticide application, removal of diseased plants, and use of resistant varieties. We are developing a simulation model of the epidemiology of RTD within a rice crop to help improve RTD risk assessment, evaluate management tactics, and identify research targets.

We have developed a prototype model that simulates virus infection dynamics

based on a set of provisional assumptions about virus and vector biology (see table). The prototype, intended to stimulate feedback from field scientists, has revealed several information gaps, such as rates of vector movement, virus acquisition, and virus transmission.

The model simulates the position and infectivity status of the vectors and the corresponding RTD infection pattern in a grid of 2,500 rice hills over 60 d.

As an illustration, the figure compares model output at 60 d after transplanting (DT) for two very simplified vector immigration situations:

a. *All immigrants infective.* Five vectors transmitting RTD spherical virus only, and 20 transmitting both spherical and bacilliform viruses, all entering the crop at 10 DT, at random positions.

b. *With additional noninfective immigrants.* As in (a), but with 100 noninfective vectors also entering the crop at 10 DT at random positions.

The greater potential for secondary virus spread in situation (b) causes an increase in the rate of disease progress (keeping in mind that this is a prototype model). We are planning a quantitative

evaluation of the potential impact of RTD management options over a range of disease development situations. □

Provisional structure and assumptions for a prototype simulation model for the spread of tungro viruses in a rice crop.

Rice	2,500 hills of an RTD/vector susceptible variety in a square grid. Each hill can be infected with either spherical or bacilliform viruses, or with both, or be uninfected.
Vectors	10,000 (maximum) <i>Nephotettix virescens</i> , allowing simulations of a single vector species at low densities (up to an av of 4 adults plus nymphs/hill).
Vector immigration	Mix of any infectivity status at my arrival time from 1 to 60 DT.
Adult age at immigration	3 d with any virus infectivity acquired the previous day.
Vector development (days after oviposition)	Egg hatch = 10, adult moult = 25, first oviposition = 30, last oviposition = 34, death = 36.
Population growth of the vector	Development is incremented daily. Population dynamics simplified with fecundity = 8 eggs/female and juvenile mortality = 0, giving effective growth rate of 4 per generation.
Vector movement	
Frequency:	4 times/d with a probability of movement between hills of 0.5 (adults) and 0.1 (nymphs).
Direction:	Random.
Distance:	Nymphs: 1 hill (100%) Adults: 1 hill (40%), 2 hills (30%), 3 hills (20%), 4 hills (10%).
Virus retention	3 d for both nymphs and adults for each virus.
Virus acquisition rate (per vector)	Probability of 0.5 after 6 h on an infected hill (but bacilliform virus is acquired only when spherical virus is present, or after access to spherical virus).
Virus transmission rate (per vector)	
Spherical virus:	Probability of 0.1 for an infective vector after 6 h on a hill.
Bacilliform virus:	Probability of 0.5 for an infective vector after 6 h on a hill (but bacilliform virus is transmitted only when spherical virus is present or after access to spherical virus).
Latent period	7 d (rice), 0 d (vector).

Simulated position and virus infectivity of vectors (left) and the pattern of infection of rice hills (right) at 60 DT; a) with all immigrants infective, and b) with additional noninfective immigrants.